
AI, EDUCATION AND CONTEMPORANEITY: FROM ENVIRONMENTS TO ASSEMBLAGES

IA, EDUCAÇÃO E CONTEMPORANEIDADE: DOS AMBIENTES ÀS ASSEMBLAGENS

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Abstract: Considering the advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) platforms in education since pandemic, the goal of this paper is to investigate the contribution of the concept of cognitive assemblage to resignify what is meant by "learning environment". Beyond the mere reproduction, in the virtual, of classroom dynamics and/or school configuration, learning environments are increasingly becoming "assemblages", that is, sets of relationships between conscious human and non-human agents (technologies) at various levels and locations, with boundaries varying as conditions and contexts change. In this sense, as a methodology, we sought to analyze documents and conclusions of academic research that address the neutral and utilitarian vision of education in relation to AI, considering it as a source of "innovation". Among the origins of this belief is the still present emancipatory and democratic perspective of the early days of the Web (1990s), but which today has been completely transformed, giving way to social concerns such as surveillance, misinformation, and algorithmic biases. We also used the experience case of the Pilares do Futuro platform (pilaresdofuturo.org.br), aimed at training educators on contemporary issues of digital citizenship; the platform is an open educational resource (OER), which encourages the sharing and "remix" of good practices by the educators themselves. It was concluded that the impacts of AI are virtually unknown (and, in some ways, underestimated) by educators and managers, and that educating for digital citizenship requires a sense of collectivity and common good present in the idea of assemblages (rather than environments).

Keywords: artificial intelligence, education, platforms, learning environmental, cognitive assemblages.

Resumo: Dado o avanço das plataformas de inteligência artificial (IA) na educação desde a pandemia, o objetivo deste artigo é investigar a contribuição do conceito de assemblagem cognitiva para ressignificar o que se entende por "ambiente de aprendizagem". Para além da mera reprodução, no virtual, da dinâmica de sala de aula e/ou da configuração escolar, ambientes de aprendizagem se tornam cada vez mais "assemblagens", isto é, conjuntos de relações entre agentes humanos conscientes e não-humanos (tecnologias) em vários níveis e locais, com limites variando conforme mudam as condições e os contextos. Nesse sentido, como metodologia, buscou-se analisar documentos e conclusões de pesquisas acadêmicas que abordam a visão neutra e utilitarista da educação em relação à IA, tida como fonte de "inovação". Dentre as origens dessa crença está a ainda presente perspectiva emancipatória e democrática dos primórdios da WEB (anos 90), mas que hoje se transformou completamente dando lugar a preocupações sociais como proteção de dados, vigilância, desinformação e vieses algorítmicos. Foi utilizado, ainda, o relato de experiência da plataforma Pilares do Futuro (pilaresdofuturo.org.br), voltada para a formação de educadores em temas contemporâneos de cidadania digital; a plataforma é um recurso educacional aberto (REA), que incentiva o compartilhamento e o "remix" de boas práticas pelos próprios educadores. Concluiu-se que os impactos da IA são praticamente desconhecidos (e, de certa forma, menosprezados) por educadores e gestores e que educar para a cidadania digital requer um senso de coletividade e bem comum presente na ideia de assemblagens (e não de ambientes).

Palavras-chave: inteligência artificial, educação, plataformas, ambientes de aprendizagem, assemblagens cognitivas.

1. INTRODUCTION

In just two months of being publicly available, the generative artificial intelligence (AI) technology ChatGPT, launched by the company OpenAI in November 2022, has reached the milestone of 100 million people registered¹ to test the new feature. No digital application has ever achieved such a large number of users in such a short space of time. This feat has been attributed to the natural language interface that makes up the technology model, simulating a "conversation" between people based on the combination of massive data collected from various online sources by the year 2021 (KOCABALLI, 2023). As highlighted by Buzato and Gonsales (2023, submitted for publication), five months before ChatGPT took over the world news agenda, the British magazine *The Economist*, on June 11, 2022, ran a cover story with the headline *AI's New Frontier*², in which it highlighted advances in the so-called "foundation models" of AI, considered the latest in machine learning, a type of technology that is based on the neuronal structure of the human brain to train algorithms using billions of data extracted from the web over the years (Big Data), data that can be text, images, sounds or all of this combined, as already contemplated in version 4 of ChatGPT (MATHIAS, 2023).

Until the spread of the Generative Pre-Trained Transformer (GPT)³ in the form of a *chatbot*⁴ and the consequent media uproar around the subject - whether to boast benefits or point out immediate dangers⁵ - discussions about the impacts of the AI foundation models used on social platforms and networks were restricted to researchers and activists. Not even the area of education, a presumed space for promoting reflection and training, had looked into the effects of AI in today's society, except to boast advantages associated with "progress

¹OpenAI receives financial support from Microsoft. Globo.com article on the rapid growth in the user base. Available at: <https://epocanegocios.globo.com/tecnologia/noticia/2023/02/chatgpt-estabelece-recorde-de-crescimento-da-base-de-usuarios-diz-ubs.ghtml>. Accessed March 27, 2023.

²AI'S NEW frontier. *The Economist*. London, June 9, 2022. Available at: <https://www.economist.com/leaders/2022/06/09/artificial-intelligences-new-frontier>. Accessed on January 8, 2023. The magazine also highlighted the 2017 article *The Attention is All You Need*, written by Google engineers introducing the Transformer foundation model. Article available at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1706.03762>. Accessed on October 20, 2023.

³ Artificial intelligence technique that uses deep machine learning to generate text similar to that produced by humans.

⁴ Software that simulates a human conversation.

⁵ For example, misinformation, biased responses, copyright infringement, among others.

and innovation” with regard to the apprehension of content (MARIOTTI; ZAUHY, 2019; GONSALES; AMIEL, 2020; CRUZ; VENTURINI, 2020; GONSALES, 2022). According to a survey commissioned by the Walton Family Foundation (2023) of 1,000 primary school teachers and 1,000 students in the US, it is teachers who have used ChatGPT the most, 51% compared to 33% of students aged between 12 and 17. The reason for this is the support that the tool offers in planning lessons, listing proposals and reducing preparation time, something that is not possible with traditional online searches that only generate results in links.

In Brazil, the spread of ChatGPT took place in an immediate post-pandemic scenario, in which schools and universities resumed face-to-face classes, but with a permanent legacy of adherence to commercial platforms that were promoted to "teaching and learning environments" (CGI.br, 2022). Although we do not yet have a specific survey on the access of Brazilian educators and students to ChatGPT, several manifestations on social networks can be found, especially foreshadowing the dreaded "copy and paste" – which had already been the focus of concerns in the early 2000s at the time of emergence of the web. In fact, annual surveys on the adoption of digital technology by schools and by children and adolescents have shown a significant rate of use of AI platforms: 78% of children with an internet connection have social media accounts and 60% of teachers use free access platforms (CETIC.br/NIC.br 2021). Increasingly considered "new" learning environments, social networks and communication and file-sharing platforms are based on the AI foundation model, which works by extracting data from its users. In other words, the apparent "free" access is actually paid for with data and metadata⁶.

AI algorithms collect metadata uninterruptedly, capturing preferences and habits to offer a different news feed for each user (PARISER, 2011). In this sense, what is usually pointed out as a benefit or convenience hides a vision of the neutrality of technology that only disguises the opacity of its operation for most people (BRIDLE, 2019; MOROZOV, 2018). The discourse of neutrality remains strong in education. Phrases such as "technology is just a tool" or "technology is neither good nor bad, it depends on what you do with it" denote the belief that simply integrating digital technology into educational processes is a sign of innovation (SCHIFF, 2021; GONSALES, 2022). The lack of knowledge on the part of education professionals about how AI works and how it affects their daily lives has been evident during

⁶ Metadata is data captured by platforms, such as geolocation, online searches, access times, connections between people, comments, audio and video capture, among others.

the COVID-19 pandemic. The urgency of so-called "remote teaching" to replace face-to-face classes pushed educational leaders and managers to adopt commercial platforms⁷ that offered free access to robust videoconferencing and file-sharing services, among others. Without reading or understanding the "conditions" of the companies' own standard terms of use, managers simply "accepted" legal documents backed by the laws of the respective countries in which these companies maintain their servers (LIMA, 2020; COBO, 2020; AMIEL et al., 2021; CHACON et al., 2023).

In his book *Big Data in Education: The digital future of learning, policy and practice* (2017), University of Edinburgh researcher Ben Williamson was one of the pioneers in the study of the advance of platforms in the field of education, pointing out how entire structures, including learning environments, previously managed by official education agencies and systems, are now the domain of large companies whose purpose has nothing to do with the right to education. These platforms are concentrated in large companies known by the acronym GAFAM - Google, Apple, Facebook, Amazon and Microsoft - (CRUZ et al., 2019), which adopt business models based on the extensive collection and extraction of data by AI technologies.

The term "virtual learning environment", or LMS (Learning Management System), can be defined as a type of digital technology created in the early 2000s to manage distance learning systems, such as making thematic content and lessons available, providing interaction between teachers and students, as well as making it possible to follow the path of each user through monitoring reports. Although online education experiences are considered a cyberculture⁸ phenomenon based on the possibilities of hypertext and interactivity (SANTOS, 2019), the context of AI platforms highlights the need to go beyond the idea of creating strategies for "using" technology. It is necessary to seek a critical understanding of how contemporary virtual environments mediate educational processes that go beyond the subject-object dichotomy, in which the human being is always the subject and the technological artifact is always the object. In this sense, the concept of cognitive assemblage,

⁷ Survey of platforms used by education departments during the pandemic, carried out by Institutos Alana, Educadigital and Intervozes. Available at: <https://onlyo.co/2VCQy9w>. Accessed on November 21, 2021.

⁸ According to Lemos (2003, p. 12), "cyberculture is the sociocultural form that emerges from the symbiotic relationship between society, culture and the new microelectronic-based technologies that emerged with the convergence of telecommunications and information technology in the [19]70s".

by researcher Katherine Hayles (2017), based on Deleuze and Guatarri (1987)⁹, is very pertinent to the reflection proposed in this article: "arrangement of systems, subsystems and individual actors through which information flows, carrying out transformations through the interpretative activities of the recognizers who operate on the flows" (p. 118). It is a cognitive composition distributed between multiple elements, humans and algorithms, so that "the cognitive decisions of each affect the others" (p.118). For Hayles (2016), a cognitive assemblage expands "the traditional view of cognition as human thought to processes that occur at various levels and locations within biological life forms and technical systems" (p. 32). Therefore, the learning environment would be an association between cognitive systems, both conscious (human beings) and non-conscious (technologies, etc.).

According to the author, a cognitive assemblage suggests a set of relationships at various levels and locations, with boundaries that vary as conditions and contexts change. Hayles' concept is similar to what is known in sociology as "socio-technical arrangements", encompassing the intrinsic relationship between technology and society, i.e. the interdependence between technical components and human beings in a given social structure (EMERY, 1993). In contemporary times, cognitive assembly, as well as socio-technical arrangements, involves considering the performativity of AI algorithms via platforms and their consequences for the social field, along the lines of what Bruno et al. (2019) call the "world laboratories":

We are facing a world-laboratory or platform science, intimately connected to the gears of the personal data market, in which a complex and growing psychic and emotional economy nurtures algorithms that claim to know us better than we know ourselves, as well as making predictions and interventions about our emotions and behavior (2019, p. 6)

In this sense, the whole world becomes a mega-laboratory, a learning environment. Through AI algorithms, effects and realities are produced via a system of recommendations which, beyond the convenience of receiving content according to preferences, can influence and/or drive the realization of the most varied actions and situations, from misinformation to the reproduction of prejudices and inequalities (BRUNO et al., 2019). For education, this is an emerging and challenging question about how to deal with the volume of environments that

⁹ "An assemblage is precisely this increase in the dimensions of a multiplicity that necessarily changes in nature as it expands its connections" (DELEUZE, GUATTARI, 1987, p. 8).

exist today - search engines, platforms, social networks, ChatGPT etc. - in which cognitive, symbolic, historical, social, geographical, architectural and structural elements permeate teaching and learning activities.

This article proposes a reflection and consequent review on what is meant by "learning environment" beyond the mere reproduction of the classroom and/or school in the virtual world. The idea of cognitive assembly contemplates the contemporary context and is close to what Buzato (2012) proposes for digital literacies: "networks of competencies, skills, texts, purposes, rules and technologies distributed across different materials, physical places and institutional regimes" (p. 786). Via a social networking platform or ChatGPT, the AI-generated answer to an advanced search or well-crafted question not only means a result in itself that will be used in a test or school assignment, but above all it means built-in advice for the company providing the AI-based service (BUZATO, 2023). Searches, links, posts, comments and various interactions represent high-value data that we deliver on a daily basis and which feeds and feeds back into the products of commercial companies. In the contemporary context, our behaviors, habits and actions become essential materials for the operation of the "world laboratory".

In order to support the proposed reflection, in addition to this introduction, the text has been organized into three topics, starting with the origins and characteristics of AI as a field of knowledge in all its multidimensionality, a fundamental but not trivial aspect for most people. In the next topic, I discuss what has come to be called Web 2.0, but which in the current context lacks foundation and yet the jargon continues to mislead normative documents for education. In the third topic, I present a report on the application of an educational project aimed at training in contemporary digital citizenship, called the Pilares do Futuro platform, which has been developed since 2020.

2. AI AND THE PLATFORMIZATION OF LIFE

In order to discuss contemporary digital culture marked by the rise of data-driven AI, it is necessary to understand the multidimensional nature of AI, which goes beyond the idea of a simple tool. One of the main scientific references regarding the origins of AI is Alan Turing, the famous English scientist whose story was portrayed in a movie¹⁰, recognized for

¹⁰ The Imitation Game. Directed by Morten Tyldum. 2014, 1h54min.

articulating a series of questions in the seminal article *Computer Machinery and Intelligence* (TURING, 1950) that influenced the foundations of the fields of cognitive science and AI (GONÇALVES, 2021). Well before Turing, however, various experiments in automation, i.e. the execution of human tasks by machines, were carried out by different scientists over the centuries, as Russell and Norvig (2010) present in their book *Artificial Intelligence - a modern approach*:

The first known calculating machine was built around 1623 by the German scientist Wilhelm Schickard (1592-1635), although the Pascaline, built in 1642 by Blaise Pascal (1623-1662), is more famous. Pascal wrote that "the arithmetical machine produces effects that seem closer to thought than all the actions of animals". Gottfried Wilhelm Leibnitz (1646-1716) built a mechanical device designed to perform operations on concepts rather than numbers, but its scope was quite limited. Leibnitz surpassed Pascal by building a calculator that could add, subtract, multiply and extract roots, whereas Pascaline could only add and subtract. Some have speculated that machines could not just do calculations, but actually be able to think and act on their own (RUSSEL; NORVIG, 2010 p. 5).

When it was designated as a field of knowledge in 1956 at the Dartmouth Conference¹¹, in the United States, there was an impetus for various studies and empirical experiments on AI to be organized over the years, although the first model of an artificial neuron had been proposed in the previous decade by Warren McCulloch and Walter Pitts (1943). In the 1980s, Geoffrey Hinton, Yoshua Bengio and Yann LeCun¹² proposed the technique of deep machine learning, which revolutionized the field, bringing AI advances in various areas, such as computer vision, natural language processing, image and sound recognition, autonomous cars, medical diagnostics, among others (GOODFELLOW et al., 2016). However, it was not until the second decade of the 2000s that AI began to gain scale and this was due to the accelerated computational development of GPU (Graphics Processing Unit) machines. Based on statistical probability with the capacity to process the gigantic availability of unstructured data, Big Data, AI continues to evolve as more and more people become active users of online services and products, constantly sharing data and metadata. Its multidimensionality is justified by the different impacts it has had on society, starting with the visible disappearance of jobs, the potential spread of disinformation, to the economic

¹¹ Proposal for organizing the Dartmouth conference, written in 1955, can be accessed at: <http://www-formal.stanford.edu/jmc/history/dartmouth/dartmouth.html>. Accessed on April 2, 2023

¹² In 2018, the three researchers received the Turing Award, awarded annually by the Association for Computing Machinery - ACM, considered the Nobel Prize in Computing. Available at: <https://amturing.acm.org/byyear.cfm>. Accessed on April 2, 2023.

concentration in large technology companies that own the development of such applications, since they require high volumes of investment¹³.

Data-driven AI operates through platforms. Terms such as "platformization" or "platform society" (DIJCK et al. 2018) have been used to designate a global ecosystem of online AI platforms¹⁴, controlled by large technology companies (Bigtechs), driven by the phenomenon of "datafication". Datafication and platformization, both linked to the rise of data-driven AI, are calling into question the character of the then longed-for emancipatory and liberating digital culture of the early days of the web in the 2000s, as the behaviors of everyday life and its economic and social flows (studying, shopping, leisure, health, dating, etc.) are now commodified information standards. Thinking about the commodification of sociocultural activity by TDIC¹⁵, researcher and free internet activist Lawrence Lessig, one of the founders of the Creative Commons open licensing system, was one of the dissenting voices at the time regarding the future of the internet as a democratic environment, warning that commercial aspects related to copyright could take over the web (LESSIG, 2000).

Today, the commercial aspects have taken on a new dimension, adding to copyright the issue of intellectual property of AI models and, in many cases, the database¹⁶, leading another notorious web personality, Tim Berners-Lee, to position himself with a plan to "save the internet", which would consist of promoting "data sovereignty", so that individuals can control the personal information that has been appropriated by Bigtechs over the years (VERDEGEM, 2021).

It is worth remembering that some reactions in terms of public policy against the excessive control of data by a few technology companies are underway, such as the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EUROPEAN UNION, 2016), in force since May 2018, and which inspired Brazil's General Personal Data Protection Law (LGPD) in force since 2020 (BRAZIL, 2018). Although the intention of these regulations is also

¹³Operating ChatGPT, for example, costs OpenAI almost USD 700,000 per day: <https://www.semianalysis.com/p/the-inference-cost-of-search-disruption>. Accessed on April 20, 2023.

¹⁴ Other recurring terms with a similar meaning are "platform capitalism" (SRNICEK, 2017) and "surveillance capitalism" (ZUBOFF, 2019), i.e. capitalism adopting the logic of the platforms that organize the ecology of apps.

¹⁵ Digital information and communication technologies.

¹⁶ Article 18 of the General Personal Data Protection Law (LGPD) (BRAZIL, 2018) states that the data subject has the right to obtain access to the data held by the controller (the one who is going to use the data), provided that "commercial and industrial secrets are observed". In other words, there is no obligation for the company that uses data in its AI model to reveal how that data was processed in order to generate a certain predictive result, as there is industrial property in relation to the procedure.

to enable citizens to have more control and decision-making power over the use of their data, they come up against a lack of knowledge about how datafication impacts on their daily lives as people and citizens, beyond the immediate conveniences detected by common sense.

In addition to permeating personal and professional relationships, as well as mobility, the way we consume and obtain information, AI operating through platforms has also raised various ethical issues, such as replicating gender and racial inequalities (SILVA, 2020; NOBLE, 2018), consolidating dominant ideological models and simplifying real life (O'NEIL, 2020), and omitting the impacts of technology on the constitution of the social and/or territorial environment, giving it a mistakenly universal character (HUI, 2020). With regard to the environment, such platforms require hardware infrastructure with high processing capacity, data centers, which are responsible for large CO₂¹⁷ emissions, a fact that citizens and even educators do not usually pay attention to.

Through the analysis of recent national and international documents and publications (2018-2021) that address AI in education, I argued (GONSALES, 2022) about the need for thought reform on the part of education professionals and public managers for the reconnection of knowledge (MORIN, 2011), considering dialogism (benefits and risks of AI), recursiveness in the relationship between humans and machines and planetary awareness (social, economic, legal and environmental impacts brought about by AI). AI is able to identify and extract patterns which, when correlated, generate predictions that are considered a type of knowledge (useful information) by those who analyze them. And this knowledge can have different meanings according to the different situations, following the intentionality of the AI model that has been built. Scholars of the interrelationship between technology and society have highlighted problems related to new forms of colonialism led by a digital industry that not only extracts data to sell behavioral predictions to the advertising market, but also needs its predictions to be accurate, which would lead to provoking and inducing human behavior (COULDRY; MEJIAS, 2019; KWET, 2019; MOROZOV, 2018; ZUBOFF, 2019). According to Zuboff (2019), private human experiences today have become commodities for datafication, since these data flows come from all kinds of interfaces: online

¹⁷ According to the International Energy Agency, data centers consume around 200 terawatt-hours (TWh) of electricity, or almost 1% of global electricity demand, contributing to 0.3% of all global CO₂ emissions. Available at: <https://www.iea.org/reports/data-centres-and-data-transmission-networks>. Accessed on Aug. 12, 2021.

searches, mobile apps, cameras, various devices, sensors, and all of this in homes, cars and cities. She details, for example, the business model based on a *behavioral surplus*:

If Google is a search company, why is it investing in smart home devices, smart wearable devices and self-driving cars? If Facebook is a social network, why is it developing drones and augmented reality? This diversity sometimes confuses outsiders, but it is often applauded as a visionary investment: eccentric bets on the future. In fact, activities that appear to be varied and even scattered across a whole random selection of industries and projects are actually all the same activity, guided by the same goal: capturing behavioral surplus (ZUBOFF, 2019, p. 163).

Morozov (2018) and Bridle (2019) argue that Silicon Valley companies impose a "technological solutionism", i.e. the belief that technology alone can solve all of society's problems. The embedded discourse promises more freedom, but actually delivers more control, as it appropriates the anxieties and insecurities of all of us users. "We continue to consider data as if it were a magical and special commodity that, on its own, could defend itself against any evil genius who dared to exploit it" (MOROZOV, 2018, p. 28). Data-driven AI has been knocking on the doors of schools and education departments from a purely utilitarian and instrumental perspective, with a focus on teaching and assessing content, something that has been evident during the pandemic (GONSALES, 2022). As Bridle (2019) points out, the uncritical and naive view of a large portion of the population persists, accepting the emancipatory discourse of new technologies, including as neutral learning "environments", when issues related to social justice, copyright, data protection, environmental sustainability, information security, among others, should be taken into account. As a multidimensional field of study, AI requires a transdisciplinary approach that presupposes an understanding of the context and new configurations (read "cognitive assemblages") brought about by AI technologies in society.

3. EDUCATION AND THE END OF WEB 2.0

The publication of an article at the end of the 1980s (BERNERS-LEE, 1989) marked the launch of the World Wide Web, which revolutionized the forms of information production with the emergence of the most diverse authorial and collaborative works, easily accessible through blogs and wikis, enhancing the possibilities for the democratization of communication and knowledge, previously restricted to the mass media and the academic environment. It was also a period marked by manifestations of tactical media and free

knowledge from a feminist perspective, which have been rescued as a digital cartographic archive by activists and researchers (VASCONCELOS et al. 2020). A number of democratic principles have permeated the web's potential as the great network of networks. Terms such as usability, access, freedoms of opinion, communication, expression and creativity were often used, and there was hope about their social and political impacts (LOVINK, 2011 apud SINGH, 2019). Authors such as Castells (1999) and Lévy (1999), who are now considered classics, have approached the web from the optimistic perspective of a network society emerging via digital information and communication technologies (DICTs), which would drive the rise of a collective intelligence - a combination of knowledge, experiences and creations - that is constantly under construction.

The term Web 2.0 emerged as a slogan after a conference organized by O'Reilly Associates (O'REILLY, 2005), emphasizing the aspect of collaboration, to foster a "participatory culture", of which Wikipedia would be the main example, but also the first social networks that emerged at that time. For Singh (2019), freedoms associated with the discourse of access and usability come in the form of participatory culture, but it hides a neoliberal vision to enable the creation of economic and technological conditions for entrepreneurial activity - currently highly leveraged by the unpaid work of users who produce content and/or establish mutual communication through a digital service. With its blunt title, *The Death of Web 2.0*, the book by British researcher Greg Singh (2019) not only declares the death of Web 2.0 but also questions whether, despite all the connectivity, people are actually connected, arguing that there is no ethics of connectivity. Even though the web apparently harbored a discourse of rapprochement, Web 2.0 was a moment in digital culture that came to an end, leaving a legacy of impacts on the well-being and mental health of people and communities. As the author points out:

The Internet, or more broadly, the digital revolution is truly changing the world at multiple levels. But it has also failed to deliver on much of the promise that was once seen as implicit in its technology. If the Internet was expected to provide more competitive markets and accountable businesses, open government, an end to corruption, and decreasing inequality—or, to put it baldly, increased human happiness—it has been a disappointment. (FOSTER; McCHESNEY, 2011 *apud* SINGH, 2019 p. 25).

Official documents that make up the current Brazilian educational technology policy - such as the Common National Curriculum Base (BNCC) (BRAZIL, 2017) - still associate the

desired development of competencies and skills with the old concept of Web 2.0, as is the case with the specific skill identified by EF69LP06:

(EF69LP06) Producing and publishing news, photo reports, photo stories, reports, multimedia reports, infographics, news podcasts, interviews, reader letters, commentaries, opinion articles of local or global interest, texts presenting and appreciating cultural production – reviews and other forms of youth culture expression, such as cultural vlogs and podcasts, gameplay, detonation, etc. – and posters, advertisements, spots, jingles for social campaigns, among others in various media, significantly experiencing the role of reporter, commentator, analyst, critic, editor or article writer, booktuber, vlogger, etc., as a way of understanding the production conditions surrounding the circulation of these texts and being able to participate and envision possibilities for participating in the language practices of the newspaper and media fields in an ethical and responsible manner, taking into account the context of Web 2.0, which expands the possibility of circulating these texts and "merges" the roles of reader and author, consumer and producer (BRAZIL, 2017, p. 140-179).

The text demonstrates a considerable gap on the part of manager-formulators about the contemporary transformations of the rise of large platforms that monopolize the way people produce and access content and which, in turn, feed AI algorithms based on data. Everyday actions (studies, shopping, leisure, meetings, etc.) are now mediated by platforms that belong to large corporations whose business model corresponds to the broad collection and extraction of data via AI technologies. Today, there is already talk of Web3¹⁸, linked to the metaverse, which has even prompted Facebook to change its name to Meta. Dijck, Poell and Wall (2018) propose that platformization challenges the concept of education as a public good:

The mechanisms of datafication, personalization, and commodification have penetrated deeply into the edifice of education, not only transforming the content of learning materials and students' learning processes but also affecting pedagogical principles as well as the organization of schools and universities. Datafication and personalization indeed raise many social, ethical, and normative questions concerning the kind of education children may engage with in the future. As a result of commodification, learning data have become a valuable currency (p. 134).

If Web 2.0 is a thing of the past and the scenario is now dominated by the phenomenon of "platformization", education needs to revisit concepts, conceptions and strategies to understand what can, in fact, be learning environments coherent with the

¹⁸Web3 differs from Web 3.0, as Professor Diogo Cortiz, from PUC-SP, explains. Available at: <https://diogocortiz.com.br/o-que-e-web3-uma-breve-historia-para-entender-de-onde-veio/>. Accessed on March 5, 2023.

search for an education quality, equitable and inclusive as indicated in the 4th UN Sustainable Development Goal (2015). The encouragement of reflective and critical debate about the constant transformations in the digital scenario is also absent in the controversial New Secondary Education (BRAZIL, 2018)¹⁹, in which the term “artificial intelligence” only appears in the guidelines of the mathematics curricular component. If technologies increasingly depend on our personal data to become more efficient and generate automated decisions, it is important to understand the constant advances and transformations of reality and our relationships with digital technology.

Some European countries, such as Germany, Denmark, Spain and France, are experiencing mobilizations by teachers' unions, students' families and activists to get schools to stop using proprietary solutions from Big Techs such as Google and Microsoft and choose free software alternatives. According to independent French media outlet Basta!, data protection agencies in two regions of Germany (Baden-Württemberg and Rhineland-Palatinate) have banned the use of Microsoft packages and videoconferencing in favor of protecting student data (KNAEBEL, 2022). And in France, there is a public policy for schools to use various open solutions through an open-source application platform²⁰. The most recent ban targeting ChatGPT was in Italy, involving the whole country, on the grounds of illegal data collection (BARBOSA, 2023).

In Brazil and in most South American countries, this critical view is practically non-existent and is restricted to activist coalitions²¹ and academic research groups, such as the Observatório Educação Viglada²², which has developed software to map the type of email server used by public universities in South America. 448 higher education institutions were mapped; 78% of them use Google and Microsoft services as an email management solution - either institutionally or in some unit (colleges or institutes) (figure 1).

¹⁹ Since the new Lula administration (2023-2026) took office, the New Secondary Education Law has been the focus of severe criticism for exacerbating inequality between public and private education and for being implemented without national direction. Various organizations and associations are calling for the law to be repealed. More details: <https://agenciabrasil.ebc.com.br/radioagencia-nacional/educacao/audio/2023-03/entidades-ligadas-educacao-pedem-revogacao-do-novo-ensino-medio>. Accessed on April 2, 2023.

²⁰ Platform link: <https://portail.apps.education.fr/signin>. Accessed on: January 19, 2023.

²¹ One example is the Coalizão Direitos na Rede, made up of more than 50 organizations, which acts in legislative advocacy to guarantee digital rights, such as freedom of expression and privacy and data protection. Website: <https://direitosnarede.org.br/>. Accessed on January 19, 2022.

²² Mapping data available at: <https://educacaoviglada.org.br>. Accessed on April 19, 2023.

Figure 1. Public university email servers under the control of Bigtechs like Google and Microsoft (red circle).
 Source: <https://educacaovigiada.org.br/pt/mapeamento/americanosul/>

By outsourcing email management, i.e. public infrastructure and data communication flows, government and public institutions are contributing to the AI training of these private companies. As Amiel et al. (2023, p. 235) point out, such an attitude "greatly reduces any possibility of local economic development and technological autonomy, creating a (historical) condition of dependence and underdevelopment". The opacity in the use of AI by these platforms, in addition to exposing educators and students to the so-called "surveillance capitalism" (ZUBOFF, 2019) and curtailing their rights such as privacy and data protection, also puts a strain on the promotion of open educational practices, which emphasize the authorship and autonomy of educational actors. Evangelista and Firmino (2020) relate Zuboff's surveillance capitalism to unequal flows of knowledge and economic surplus between the rich economies of the Global North - where corporations are based - and the dependent economies of the Global South. The Rede Nacional de Pesquisa (RNP), which was created in 1985 with the aim of providing a Brazilian Internet network infrastructure for academia, has now become a broker²³, intermediating the contracting of different external suppliers (among them, Google, Microsoft, Amazon etc) (GROSSMAN; COSTA, 2017).

²³ Terms used in the technology area for a company or institution that is an intermediary between the purchase and sale of digital services.

It is essential that educational institutions and public managers understand how the business models of "free" platforms work, or even those that are paid for with public funds. Likewise, training policies for education professionals - from management to classroom practice - need to be associated with research and studies that problematize the transformations that this new technological context (with ideologies and interaction patterns) brings and suggest "cognitive assemblages" in geopolitical power structures that cannot be ignored (HAYLES, 2017; BUZATO, 2023).

4. PILARES DO FUTURO: DIGITAL CITIZENSHIP PRACTICES

By adopting the expanded definition of learning environments as cognitive assemblages, in the view of HAYLES (2017), rather than mere management systems that reproduce traditional teaching models in digital form, it is necessary to consider possible paths for teaching and educational management that take into account training in contemporary digital citizenship. In this sense, as an educator at the head of a non-governmental educational institution and a researcher in digital technologies since 2012, I have been working on the development of experiential teacher training projects focused on the dissemination of open educational resources and practices, the latter defined as:

[...] the combination of a set of educational actions guided by an ethical principle, strongly linked to the ideals of Social Justice, Equity and Transparency, materialized through the various teaching activities (planning, teaching, assessment, syllabus, activities, content, didactics and resources), whose main objective is to provide experiences that enable the generation of knowledge and learning through sharing and the establishment of a collaborative network, in which people from different relational levels (peers, external network, students and educators) contribute, benefiting from new media to promote individual and collective objectives without, however, considering them a necessary condition for their realization (SOUSA, 2022, p. 45).

The comprehensive interpretation by researcher Janaina Sousa (2022), the result of her master's dissertation, in which she used one of my projects as a case study - the Líder Educação Aberta online course - reveals a cognitive assemblage by highlighting in words the network of relationships and interactions that are established for an open educational practice to materialize. As Buzato (2023) pointed out, citing Hayles (2017), cognitive assemblages occur through a set of processes, information flows, cultural signs and other

collective productions resulting from connected human and non-human interactants. When considering the current context of predictive (platforms) or generative (ChatGPT and similar) AIs, the author argues that:

[...] thinking about the assembly tells us that it is smarter to worry less about finding AI plagiarism-detecting AIs for college entrance exam essays and more about what an ("algorithmic") college entrance exam essay actually says about "intelligence"; or to invest less in fancy educational AIs and more in time and encouragement for research, self-development and creative autonomy for teachers who can delegate "banking model of education" tasks to "honest" AIs in exchange for more meaningful human-human interaction (BUZATO, 2023, p. 9).

Organized in partnership with the UNESCO Chair in Distance Education at the University of Brasilia in 2020 and 2021, the Líder Educação Aberta course²⁴ had the objective of forming a network of 200 leading educators in the dissemination of knowledge related to collaboration and the sharing of open concepts and practices. One of the course activities, carried out synchronously and asynchronously in the Moodle environment²⁵ consisted of exploring, analyzing and contributing content to the Pilares do Futuro platform, designed²⁶ and launched in 2020 by the Instituto Educadigital, of which I am the founder, with institutional support from the Núcleo de Tecnologia do Ponto Br (NIC.br) and UNESCO Brazil Representation, to encourage exchanges between educators on how to plan and implement educational practices in digital citizenship. Course participants were asked to create from scratch or remix a practice already published by the platform's editorial team, adapting it according to their needs or coming up with new ideas. The platform was also one of the focus environments for collaborative work in the classroom with undergraduate pedagogy students from two public universities, the State University of Minas Gerais (UEMG) and the University of Brasília (UNB) (AMIEL; DINIZ, 2023).

The name "Pilares do Futuro" refers to the four pillars of education launched by UNESCO at the end of the 1990s, but which remain highly relevant and challenging in today's society: learning to know, learning to do, learning to live together and learning to be (DELORS, 1996). The expression "pilares" (pillars) also has to do with a base, a foundation,

²⁴ Information about the course at <https://aberta.org.br/cursolider/>. Accessed on November 21, 2023

²⁵ Book software environment for organizing and managing remote teaching and learning

²⁶ The idea for the platform arose from a conversation with educator Rosa Lamana, who is also a career civil servant at the São Paulo State Department of Education, who approached me about organizing a book of good practices together, and it was then that I suggested we create the platform.

which supports the idea that educating for digital citizenship must be something constant and solid, considering the transformations in society. And "futuro" (future), in the words of Hayles (2005, p. 18) "will be what we collectively make of it" based on reflective questions such as "What do we want the future to be? What values should command the commitment of our senses, thoughts and actions?"(p.18). In other words, how can we guarantee a digital future in which promoting the common good is actually a more plausible goal than private profit interests?

Pilares do Futuro offers the opportunity to rethink the relationship between education and so-called TDICs²⁷, in order to break with the entrenched view of technology as a mere "tool" for teaching content – still very present in educational policies – to embrace critical digital literacy about the assemblages involving AI in society (BUZATO; GONSALES, submitted for publication). Part of the Pilares do Futuro collection are practices that combine reflective propositions on current issues and hands-on productions so that teachers and students can have the opportunity to learn together. Here are three examples:

- "Can algorithms spread racism?" - discusses the workings of social networks' AI algorithm, which uses large volumes of data to induce what each person wants to see in their feed and, even though it seems like a convenience for users, there is concern about spreading prejudice and threatening human rights.²⁸
- "Loyalty risks of proprietary software" – presents the differentiation between proprietary software and free software, with the intention of sparking discussion about the dependency condition that most software generates in its users.²⁹
- "Did you know the cloud does not exist?" - emphasizes the physical infrastructure of the internet, especially the servers (data centers), often referred to as the "cloud", causing a misunderstanding of how the internet works. This practice was one of those chosen and remixed by the educators taking part in the Líder Educação Aberta course.³⁰

²⁷Acronym for digital information and communication technologies (DICT).

²⁸Practice available at: <https://pilaresdofuturo.org.br/praticas/algorithmo-pode-ser-racista/>. Accessed on May 2, 2023

²⁹Practice available at: <https://pilaresdofuturo.org.br/praticas/solucoes-em-plataformas-livres-e-os-riscos-de-fidelizacao-aos-sofwares-proprietarios/>. Accessed on May 2, 2023

³⁰Practice available at: <https://pilaresdofuturo.org.br/praticas/voce-sabia-que-a-nuvem-nao-existe/> already remixed/adapted: <https://pilaresdofuturo.org.br/praticas/a-nuvem-nao-e-onipresente/>. Accessed on May 2, 2023.

The platform was built from an authorial taxonomy specially developed for Wordpress (a free software web content management system) and later made available in an open code sharing repository³¹ between programmers. Educators interested in contributing should register with their full name and e-mail address and fill in a form to describe a proposed practice or report on a practice that has been carried out and can be reproduced. In short, the fields requested are: motivating context, methodology and resources used, expected results and references. Once the practice is uploaded to the platform, a committee of educator curators reads it and suggests improvements, such as asking for a more detailed description of the methodology or an adjustment to the references provided. According to Inbar (1996), it is everyday educational practices that bring about innovation, in other words, it is practices that make it possible for concerns and ideas to be put into practice, favoring re-significations, adaptations and reorganizations of activities and processes in school culture. It is worth mentioning, however, the challenging situation of working on this issue in the classroom, because although there are many guidance materials (especially on safe and responsible use of the internet), there are few references to concrete practices to be implemented. Furthermore, the experience with the teacher-authors of practice who are already taking part has shown that the habit of sharing one's own content and/or idea so that another teacher can reproduce and/or adapt it is not yet as widespread as had been hoped, either culturally or technically (such as writing a practice report) (GONSALES, 2021).

The most recent practice published by the editorial team, in April 2023, highlights ChatGPT, the hype of the moment where this article began. Although we do not have a survey on the access of educators and students, as mentioned in the introduction, we can already see an accumulation of suggestions, lists on the social networks³² and even intensive courses on how to "use" it in education, favoring a utilitarian view that lacks depth in relation to the social, economic and political impacts of such generative AI technology. With the title "ChatGPT: far beyond its use in education"³³, the practice proposes an approach that encourages teachers and students to understand the workings behind the artifact, without having to use it (without having to access the system and register). Using different colored

³¹Code available at: <https://gitlab.com/EducacaoAberta>. Accessed on August 12, 2023

³²Dom Cabral Foundation's Innovation Coordination lists 30 ideas for using ChatGPT: <https://sejarelevante.fdc.org.br/30-usos-do-chatgpt-em-experiencias-de-aprendizagem/>. Accessed on April 24, 2023.

³³Practice available at <https://pilaresdofuturo.org.br/praticas/chatgpt-muito-alem-do-uso-na-educacao/>. Accessed on October 20, 2023.

building blocks, the idea is to visually represent the different data and sources that have been captured by AI over the years so that ChatGPT can perform by simulating a "humanized" conversation. Also, throughout the development of the proposal, the practice draws attention to the problem of data protection, i.e. our data (such as questions and feedback) is largely captured to train and improve the functioning of the technology.

Still in Inbar's view (1996), the purpose of *Pilares do Futuro* is to induce changes in the traditional ways of working on the issue of digital citizenship, as it shifts the focus from the individual responsibility of "think before you post" to the understanding that there is, in fact, a collective responsibility of the ecosystem that needs to be taken into account: the functioning of data-based AI platforms feeds back on the generation of attention, and the power of the companies that own these platforms is only increasing, and with that comes government regulations, etc. "Education finds itself engaged in an endless attempt to bridge the gap between the present and the future" (p. 21). In this sense, an online platform can more quickly keep up with the necessary changes and updates over time, something that printed materials cannot because they are dated. It should also be pointed out that the platform favors the promotion of human rights education (CANDAUI, 2007) in schools' political pedagogical projects as a cross-cutting axis that affects the entire syllabus.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This article sought to present a new vision for what have come to be characterized as "learning environments", much in evidence with the pandemic situation in which schools have had to resort to commercial data-driven AI platforms - be it learning management or social media - to replace face-to-face teaching. Commonly associated with the mere reproduction of face-to-face classroom dynamics, learning environments are understood as neutral technical systems through which content is transmitted. Even though they allow interactive tasks such as forums or messaging, the different agencies that are established between human beings, machines and contexts and their interrelationships are not usually considered.

In this sense, I highlighted the concept of "cognitive assemblage", by Hayles (2017), which is based on the work of philosophers Deleuze and Guattari in which the term

"assembly" indicates the combination of different and diverse agents, whether human or not, generating a non-hierarchical relationship, but a distributed one. As the author points out, the probable intertwining between human beings and intelligent machines "only deepens and broadens the need for a debate based on principles, because the future cannot be seen apart from the primary concern with ethics that should guide these discussions" (HAYLES, 2005 p. 148).

Faced with the accelerated advance of AI platforms belonging to large technology corporations, there is an urgent need to revisit not only what is meant by a learning environment, either in the misconception about its neutrality or in its characteristic of an agent, favoring the establishment of cognitive assemblages whose in-depth and critical understanding requires investment in training. The experience reported with the Pilares do Futuro open platform, which has been running since 2020, points to a possible path for education professionals and students to understand the current context of digital society, which involves critical literacy about the ways in which AI technologies are developed and operated to mediate educational activities and processes. As an application, Pilares do Futuro combines theory and practice with a view to generating more awareness about the constantly evolving digital ecosystem, highlighting solutions through collective training actions. Because they are open resources, the practices and suggestions published on the platform can be freely shared, modified and improved. Therefore, "educating for digital citizenship" involves prioritizing values and ethical issues desired for a digital future in which there will probably be more and more AI technologies.

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HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE

GONSALES, Priscila. IA, education and contemporaneity: from environments to assemblages. **Passagens: Revista do Programa de Pós-Graduação em Comunicação da Universidade Federal do Ceará, Fortaleza**, v. 14, n. esp., p. 54-81, dez. 2023. Tradução: Vanessa Stelzer e Priscila Gonsales.